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D6.4 – Blue-Cloud Stakeholders engagement and synergies, 1st report

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructure
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WB	Workbench

Keywords

Synergy, Cooperation, EOSC, DTO, marine science, VLab, VRE, WB, DD&AS.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Since the launch of Blue-Cloud 2026, the project team has proactively worked on establishing strong partnerships and synergies with other projects and initiatives in the Open Science and DTO environments, aiming to create long-lasting relationships to attain the Blue-Cloud's long-term objectives. The team strongly believes that through collaboration and cooperation with initiatives operating in similar fields, the value of Blue Cloud services increases.

As output of this effort to cluster with related projects and initiatives in Europe and beyond, the first version of the Blue-Cloud Stakeholder engagement and synergies report presents an overview of all the projects Blue-Cloud 2026 has established cooperations within the first two years (M24).

The dialogues established so far represent the ground layer for collaborations to be pursued in the second half of the project's lifetime, leveraging on the public availability of the Blue-Cloud services (VRE, V Labs, WBs) and the wealth of data resources of Blue-Cloud.

This document represents a first release of the Blue-Cloud Stakeholder engagement and synergies and a second release (D6.5) will be produced by M40.

The document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 provides a general introduction and outlines the objectives of the deliverable.
- Chapter 2 gives an overview of Blue-Cloud's role in the open science and DTO environments.
- Chapter 3 explains the approach used to monitor the status of established synergies and identify new ones.
- Chapter 4 details the synergies established within the EOSC remit.
- Chapter 5 focuses on the synergies formed under the Digital Twin of the Ocean initiative.
- Chapter 6 highlights the collaborations fostered during the 1st Blue-Cloud Federation Workshop.
- Chapter 7 outlines synergies established with other projects and initiatives.
- Chapter 8 draws the conclusions and summarises the next steps.

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1. Introduction

Since the launch of Blue-Cloud 2026, the project team has established relationships with key players in the blue economy, open science, and digital twin of the ocean environments. These collaborations have grown throughout the project's duration, helping to increase Blue-Cloud's visibility within the marine community. Furthermore, establishing synergies has supported Blue-Cloud in advancing with technical developments, all crucial elements to drive forward the project's exploitation and sustainability plan.

Providing practical frameworks to establish long-term collaborations with external partners has also proved to be a key element in expanding Blue-Cloud user base, amplifying the effect of the Blue-Cloud's main achievements and engaging with other communities working in marine and environmental research. Following the work started in the first pilot of Blue-Cloud H2020 initiative, the project team has continued to strengthen the cooperation with key projects and initiatives in the marine ecosystem, in the broad European open science framework and, as a novelty for Blue-Cloud 2026, with the EU DTO framework, by focusing on opportunities that revolve around the Blue-Cloud main assets.

The following sections present the work carried out by the Blue-Cloud team, in the first two years from its launch.

2. Overview of Blue-Cloud in the Open Science and DTO environments

Blue-Cloud operates in the framework of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), under which programme it was conceived and funded ([HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-03: FAIR and open data sharing in support of healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters](#)). The Blue-Cloud Service platform features a variety of services that can be used for undertaking world-class science via the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem, by featuring leading operational marine research infrastructures and e-infrastructures. In the Blue-Cloud federation, Blue research infrastructures (Ris) and other data and service infrastructures and technological providers make their services available to the community via agreed, FAIR formats and technology and standards and best practices supporting data exchange and interoperability, that EOSC recommends or accepts.

Blue-Cloud plays an important role in Open Science, particularly in marine research, by integrating a wide range of data and services to promote collaboration and innovation. The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a state-of-the-art cyber platform designed to implement an incubator of new research ideas, supporting scientists and researchers in designing, testing, and evaluating innovative computational models that extract valuable knowledge from diverse datasets, while accelerating open science and collaborative research in ocean sustainability. The Blue-Cloud VRE offers a suite of common

services and tools, including cloud storage, computing resources, collaborative workspaces, R-Studio, JupyterHub, JupyterLab, Galaxy, a Software Importer, and an Analytics Engine. These tools empower researchers to create and manage Virtual Laboratories (Vlabs), facilitating seamless collaboration by enabling the efficient sharing of research artifacts and effective communication. By integrating with the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service, the framework promotes FAIR data principles and enables the exploration of diverse datasets. This innovative approach enhances the EOSC ecosystem by providing a flexible and user-friendly platform for collaborative research, data-intensive applications, and reproducible workflows.

At the same time, Blue-Cloud supports the [EC Mission Ocean European Digital Twin of the Ocean \(European DTO\) programme](#), which aims to model the ocean's multiple components, provide knowledge and understanding of the past and present and create trustable predictions of its future behaviour. Blue-Cloud supports the development of applications that could be later deployed on EDITO -the public infrastructure of the European DTO- for long-term sustainability and reuse, empowering scientists with additional tools and applications to model, simulate, and analyse complex marine processes in real-time.

3. The approach of the Blue-Cloud synergy programme

Since the project kick-off meeting, the Blue-Cloud 2026 team has launched the *Synergy Programme*, a structured framework for continuous engagement with projects and initiatives within the European marine research ecosystem. This approach was initially developed and implemented during the first Blue-Cloud pilot. As it proved to be successful it was adopted also in Blue-Cloud 2026.

The *Synergy Programme* follows four key steps:

1. **Building an Inventory of Initiatives:** The team has created a comprehensive inventory of relevant projects and initiatives for Blue-Cloud. This inventory is periodically updated by the consortium whenever a new, promising initiative is identified. At the time of writing this deliverable, the inventory includes 54 initiatives.
2. **Initiating Engagement:** Once potential synergies are identified, the Trust-IT team (leader of Task 6.3 - Stakeholders engagement and synergies) organises an introductory call with representatives of the identified initiatives and the Blue-Cloud team. The purpose of this call is to define the scope of the synergy—whether technical/scientific, policy-related, or communication-focused.
3. **Steering Board Review:** A summary of synergy activities is presented during the monthly meetings with the Blue-Cloud Steering Board to gather feedback, share updates, and ensure alignment with project objectives.

4. **Follow-Up Activities:** Regular follow-up calls are conducted to monitor the status of collaborations and ensure the progress of the established synergies.

Initiative Name	Stakeholder category	Initiative type	Coordination Country	Main area	URL
Aqualnra	Scientific, Research & Academia	HE project	Denmark	Infrastructure for Marine and Inland Water Research	https://aqualnra
PREP4BLUE	Scientific, Research & Academia	HE project	France	Research and Innovation for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters	https://prep4blue
FAIR-Ease	Scientific, Research & Academia	HE project	France	Interdomain digital architecture for integrated use of environm	https://fairease.e
Marco Bolo	Scientific, Research & Academia	HE project	France	Marine Coastal Biodiversity Long-term Observations	https://cordis.eur
ILIAD	Scientific, Research & Academia	H2020 project	Belgium	Digital Twin of the Ocean	https://www.ocea
EDITO infra/ModelLi	Scientific, Research & Academia	HE project	France	Digital Twin of the Ocean	https://edito-infra
CLIMAREST	Ocean Observation, data and modelling institutions	Mission Lighthouse project	Norway	Lighthouse project related to the EU Mission Restore our Ocea	https://climarest
DTO-BioFlow	Ocean Observation, data and modelling institutions	HE project	Belgium	Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin	https://dto-bioflow
IMAGINE	Ocean Observation, data and modelling institutions	HE project	Netherlands	Establishing a dedicated iMagine AI framework and platform f	https://www.imac

Figure 1 – a printscreen of the inventory of the initiatives

After sharing updates with the project’s team, all relevant information about the synergies is uploaded into a dedicated section on the Blue-Cloud website, called [Synergies](#).

4. Blue-Cloud synergies under the EOSC remit

4.1. Technical federation

Blue-Cloud is an Open Science platform designed to support collaborative marine research by bringing together various datasets, tools, and services in line with Open Science principles. As the [EOSC Federation](#) evolves, one of the key exploitation pathways that Blue-Cloud is exploring is becoming an EOSC Thematic Node for marine research. This initiative aligns with an ongoing assessment of requirements for EOSC nodes that the consortium is undertaking, which includes technical and organizational interaction with the EOSC EU node, relations with other nodes, legal representation, mechanisms for long-term funding, quality service provision and monitoring, capacity to onboard third-party services, contribution to EOSC core capabilities, compliance with EOSC federation rules, standards and best practices, community building, and legal status.

According to Requirements for EOSC Nodes draft document (May 2024), EOSC Nodes will be the entry points for end users to the entire EOSC Federation, with each node offering its own services of other providers (‘third-party’ services onboarded to the EOSC Node), in compliance with the EOSC Federation’s common rules and requirements as well as the own policies of the EOSC Node. Nodes will offer (scientific) services and/or data that adhere the FAIR principles and recognized standards and best practices, including curated research outputs (such as publications, datasets, software, etc.), specialised knowledge,

applications, tools, infrastructure and/or platform services, and/or data processing and storage capabilities.

Blue-Cloud EOSC Marine Node DRAFT for DISCUSSION

Figure 2 – draft schema of the Blue-Cloud EOSC thematic node

The main benefits of becoming an EOSC node are summarised below:

- **Blue-cloud pilot thematic EOSC** can be assessed as a model for the development of other thematic clouds. The cyber-platform of Blue-Cloud provides FAIR access to multidisciplinary data, analytical tools and computing and storage facilities that support research that will be improved if brought up to an EOSC Federated level. APIs to access blue services will be updated to complement EOSC-based services.
- **Real-life demonstrators** for web-based open science will be available for testing by research communities in the EOSC federation. Each VLab comprises a series of applications for data processing, publishing of data results, and managing computation routines as well as collaboration services. They provide open science-friendly working environments for users to analyse datasets and (re)generate research products for performing research in biodiversity to environmental science, as well as fisheries and aquaculture. The demonstrators can be adapted to other regions or research fields and their processes improved by inputs from other cases of use. The scientific products will be expanded and further exploited by a richer community, and this will boost Blue-Cloud’s sustainability.

- **Blue-Cloud methodology** for researchers interacting with e-infrastructure developers will benefit from the interaction with developers from other infrastructures. Workflows and practices, while built upon generic core principles and services, will be challenged to meet other scientific needs. In this way, Blue-Cloud will have the opportunity to contribute to FAIR formats, technology standards and best practices that suit the marine community.
- The data-intensive **Workbenches for selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)** will be proposed as new ways for adopting additional cloud storage, cloud computing, deep learning and neural networks for supporting big data processes for validation, extraction, interpolation and product generation, to be further exploited in a Green Deal Data Lakes or EDITO Data Lake framework.

To support this infrastructure, Blue-Cloud is built around the use of e-infrastructures. The following paragraphs explain the role of these e-infrastructures and how they support Blue-Cloud.

4.2. EGI

EGI supports the interactive data analytics environments for Blue-Cloud: a JupyterHub development environment that provides users access to the JupyterLab interface for interactive execution of notebooks combining text, code and visualisations and access to RStudio platform for statistical analysis with R.

EGI also supports federated login to [D4Science](#) with the EGI Check-in service, with multiple authentication sources available: eduGAIN and social accounts, and ensuring compatibility with EOSC AAI.

4.2.1. EGI's Service Level Agreement

To formalise the provision and support of EGI's essential services, Blue-Cloud and EGI have signed a **Service Level Agreement (SLA)** in November 2023. This agreement outlines the various types of resource allocation for services provided by EGI, including *Pledged resources*, which are reserved for the community, *Opportunistic resources*, which depend on local availability, and *Time allocation*, which grants resources for a fixed period. The core services outlined in the SLA include *Cloud Compute*, *Online Storage*, and *Check-In*, each supported by additional services such as accounting and service monitoring to ensure proper functioning.

EGI Foundation is responsible for monitoring the services and ensuring the fulfilment of the agreed service-level targets. It also retains the right to make changes to how the service is provided, in which case the Customer will be promptly informed, and the agreement will be updated accordingly.

Blue-Cloud, as the Customer, plays a crucial role in ensuring the services provided by EGI are acknowledged in all related scientific publications. This is done by incorporating a specific

acknowledgement in the work. Blue-Cloud also ensures compliance with the terms outlined in the agreement, including the prohibition of sharing access credentials, adhering to the Acceptable Use Policy (AUP), and ensuring that the data stored within the services does not violate any legal restrictions.

Additionally, Blue-Cloud is responsible for managing Virtual Organisations (VOs), ensuring that the appropriate group of users is entitled to access the services and that all information is kept up to date within the EGI Operations Portal.

The signature of the SLA helps Blue-Cloud and EGI to follow a structured collaboration that ensures the full use of EGI's infrastructure to support marine and environmental research, providing both high-performance computing and secure data storage solutions.

4.3. EUDAT

[EUDAT](#) provides a range of data management services and storage resources across Europe, supporting various research communities through its network of academic computing and data centres in 15 European countries. These resources are paired with some of Europe's most powerful supercomputers, allowing researchers to store, access, and process their data in a secure environment, as part of the EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI). EUDAT aims to connect research infrastructures with e-infrastructures by engaging with the research community, and it receives support from the EU Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) and the EU Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (DG CONNECT).

As part of the wider Blue Cloud framework, EUDAT works alongside other e-infrastructures building on existing resources to contribute to the development of the framework.

EUDAT offers a set of key services within the Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI), which include:

- *B2SAFE*: A service for securely replicating research data.
- *B2STAGE*: Helps move data to computational resources for processing.
- *B2FIND*: A tool to help researchers find datasets.
- *B2SHARE*: A service for storing, sharing, and publishing research data.
- *B2DROP*: Allows data synchronisation and exchange between users.

EUDAT also provides essential operational services for managing the CDI:

- *B2ACCESS*: A secure and easy-to-use authentication and authorisation platform.

- *B2HANDLE*: Manages persistent identifiers (PIDs) for data objects, similar to DOIs for research papers.
- *B2HOST*: A framework that allows communities to deploy and run their own applications and services close to the data storage.

EUDAT plays an important part in the Blue-Cloud framework by using its B2SERVICES (B2ACCESS, B2SAFE, B2STAGE, B2HOST, and B2DROP) to contribute to key activities within the Blue-Cloud project. Its contributions include:

- *Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS)*: EUDAT helps as a data broker by retrieving datasets from the federated Blue-Cloud data infrastructures and temporarily storing them with associated metadata.
- *Data Delivery*: EUDAT ensures datasets are delivered to users or pushed into the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for use in Virtual Labs (VLabs), where they can be analysed and visualised.
- *Interoperability*: EUDAT contributes to making the Blue-Cloud DD&AS and VRE product catalogues accessible via the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) portal using standard protocols.

By integrating EUDAT’s services, Blue-Cloud provides researchers with streamlined access to important data and computational tools, helping advance research in marine and environmental sciences.

4.4. Sharing common approaches and best practices for data analysis: signed MoUs

To promote best practices in data analysis, Blue-Cloud has established strategic synergies with two European projects, FAIR-EASE and CLIMAREST, both of which have developed dedicated Virtual Labs (VLabs) within the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE).

These collaborations focus on improving data accessibility and interoperability across research fields. By working together and sharing technical infrastructures like VREs, Blue-Cloud 2026, FAIR-EASE, and CLIMAREST aim to tackle important challenges in marine and Earth sciences. The shared efforts and community activities are expected to make data-intensive research more effective, reproducible, and accessible.

The following paragraphs present the main scope of the established synergies.

4.5. FAIR-EASE

The main objective of FAIR-EASE is to customise and operate distributed and integrated services for the observation and modelling of the Earth system, environment and biodiversity by improving their different components implemented in close cooperation with user-communities, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and research infrastructures in their design and sustainable availability.

In order to strengthen their cooperation, on 6 November 2024, Blue-Cloud 2026 and FAIR-EASE signed an MoU to formalise their collaboration and strengthen their common goal in advancing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data practices.

This MoU establishes a framework for cooperation between the two projects. Key areas of collaboration include:

- Establishing a working group on data access to share best practices and approaches for accessing and analysing data.
- Exploring the setup and use of a shared data lake to enhance data storage and processing efficiency.
- Facilitating the integration and testing of FAIR-EASE components within Blue-Cloud's Virtual Research Environment.
- Organising joint webinars and knowledge-sharing sessions to enhance community engagement and capacity building.
- Establishing a working group on impact pathways to ensure the sustainability and exploitability of project results, including considering and aligning with EDITO developments.

A dedicated [Press Release](#) has also summarised the main achievements gained through this collaboration.

Figure 3 – The Blue-Cloud’s and FAIR-EASE’s coordinators after the MoU signature

4.5.1. The FAIR-EASE Virtual Laboratories in the Blue-Cloud’s VRE

As part of the cooperation between Blue-Cloud and FAIR-EASE, the FAIR-EASE team has developed and started utilising two dedicated Virtual Laboratories (VLabs): **Coastal Water Dynamics** and **Marine Omics Observations**.

- *Marine Omics Observations VLab*: This VLab serves as a FAIR-EASE project pilot for finding, browsing, interrogating, and analysing metagenomic data products (including DNA sequence data). These data products are derived from the analysis of EMO BON sample data using the MetaGOflow analysis pipeline.
- *Coastal Water Dynamics VLab*: This VLab acts as another FAIR-EASE project pilot, offering users online tools and services for gridding, model/data intercomparison, data analysis, and visualisation. These services are powered by tools such as DIVAnd, SOURCE, and ODV/webODV.

The usage statistics of the VLabs show a positive trend in terms of user engagement. While both VLabs are currently private and accessible only to project partners, the number of FAIR-EASE consortium members actively using the VLabs has grown over time.

- VLab Access Trends:** While the number of individual users has increased, the frequency of Virtual Research Environment (VRE) accesses does not follow the same growth pattern. This is because VRE accesses depend on specific activities such as testing the platform, using storage resources, and uploading documents.
- Coastal Water Dynamics Usage:** This VLab saw higher activity during its initial phase, as team members focused on understanding and testing the platform’s capabilities.
- Marine Omics Observations Usage:** This VLab makes extensive use of Jupyter Notebooks, which combine code, outputs (e.g., graphs and tables), and narrative text in a single document. This makes it easier to reproduce experiments and analyses. The increased activity in this VLab, particularly during September and October (as shown in Figures 5 and 6), is attributed to intensive usage of the Jupyter Notebook feature. This tool has been instrumental in allowing users to rerun code, verify results, and extend their work.

The Figures below summarise the main statistics of the FAIR-EASE VLabs usage.

Figure 4 – Users of the FAIR-EASE VLabs users

Figure 5 – VRE accesses in the FAIR VLABs

Figure 6 – Access to the Jupyter notebook from the Marine Omics Observations VLab

4.6. CLIMAREST

The CLIMAREST project focuses on restoring marine ecosystems across the Arctic and Atlantic through a holistic, interdisciplinary approach. It prioritises fragile habitats such as Arctic oligotrophic coastal areas, seagrass meadows, shallow-water rocky bottoms, oyster reefs, and soft bed benthic habitats, which are vital for biodiversity and particularly vulnerable to disturbance.

The project also aims to develop, test, and evaluate a general framework for restoring degraded coastal habitats. This framework, supported by research at demonstration sites, is designed to be scalable and adaptable, offering policymakers practical tools and protocols to enhance climate resilience and improve restoration efforts across the region.

To strengthen their collaboration, Blue-Cloud 2026 and CLIMAREST signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on 21 November 2024. This formal agreement underlines their shared commitment to advancing research and innovation in marine and coastal ecosystem resilience, restoration, and sustainable management.

The MoU provides a framework for cooperation in key areas:

- *Data Integration*: CLIMAREST will contribute biodiversity monitoring and human impact data to the EMODnet portal, enhancing the datasets federated by Blue-Cloud 2026.
- *Virtual Research Environments (VREs)*: CLIMAREST will use Blue-Cloud's VREs for pilot projects and will explore further technical integration and service deployment.
- *Knowledge Sharing*: The projects will exchange expertise to guide Blue-Cloud's strategic roadmap and support the development of CLIMAREST's holistic toolbox.
- *Community Engagement*: Both projects will collaborate on webinars, hackathons, and training activities to promote knowledge sharing and wider collaboration.

A [press release](#) has been prepared to highlight this important partnership and promote the cooperation between the two projects.

Figure 7 – The Blue-Cloud 2026 and CLIMAREST project coordination teams at the MoU signature

4.6.1. The CLIMAREST Virtual Laboratory in the Blue-Cloud’s VRE

As part of this collaboration, the CLIMAREST team has developed and begun using a dedicated Virtual Laboratory (VLab).

The **CLIMAREST Ecological Restoration Lab** leverages JupyterHub to host a series of notebooks designed to facilitate interactive data exploration and analysis. These notebooks include Markdown text, interactive widgets to toggle between pre-created scenarios, and dynamic visualisations such as interactive figures created with Plotly. Initially, a local version will be developed and shared with project partners to gather feedback and evaluate its effectiveness as a solution before finalising the choice of libraries or tools. R Shiny is also being considered as an alternative to achieve similar functionalities.

Statistics related to the usage of the VLab highlight its growing adoption within the CLIMAREST consortium. While, as for the FAIR-EASE V Labs, the VLab is private and can be used only by the CLIMAREST team members, this trend indicates increasing interest from team members in testing and engaging with the Virtual Laboratory.

A similar trend is observed for access to the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and Jupyter notebooks. The team has specifically requested access to Jupyter notebooks to perform analyses, particularly for creating visualisations and generating computational outputs. The highest level of activity is anticipated in April 2024, with increased use of the Jupyter notebooks to perform key restoration-related analyses.

The Figures below summarises the main activities performed by the CLIMAREST VLab.

Figure 8 – Ecological Restoration Lab Users

Figure 9 – Number of accesses to the VRE and Jupyter

4.7. Flexibility of the Blue-Cloud's VLabs

The examples provided by FAIR-EASE and CLIMAREST demonstrate the flexibility of building VLabs on the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE). As a matter of fact, the VLabs can be tailored to meet the specific needs of individual projects, such as the distinct requirements of the Coastal Water Dynamics, Marine Omics Observations and Ecological Restoration VLabs.

4.8. AI4EOSC

[AI4EOSC](#) (Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud) is a key initiative in the realm of scientific and industrial research. Its primary focus is leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI), Deep Learning (DL), and Machine Learning (ML) to harness the increasing volume of big data. Addressing the growing need for machine and deep learning applications, AI4EOSC seeks to enhance the range of services available through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Building on the achievements of the DEEP-Hybrid-DataCloud H2020 project, AI4EOSC provides researchers with advanced tools and services. By prioritising the accessibility and FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) of data and research outputs, the project aims to accelerate research progress across Europe.

Blue-Cloud and AI4EOSC are working towards integrating their respective platforms: the **AI4EOSC marketplace** and the **Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)**. To realise this goal, the collaboration will focus on the following steps:

- *Authentication and Authorisation Mechanisms*: Implement systems enabling Blue-Cloud users to access a customised version of the AI4EOSC platform, while allowing AI4EOSC users to utilise the Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS) and other Blue-Cloud services.
- *Identification of a Virtual Laboratory (VLab) or Workbench (WB)*: Select a specific VLab or WB within Blue-Cloud to facilitate access to the AI4EOSC platform.
- *Platform Integration*: Incorporate Blue-Cloud services into the AI4EOSC platform to create a more cohesive and comprehensive research ecosystem. The image below presents the AI4EOSC marketplace with the services offered as of December 2024. Through this synergy, the offer of the marketplace could be further increased with the services offered by Blue-Cloud.

Figure 10 – The AI4EOSC Marketplace with the services offered as of December 2024

5. Blue-Cloud synergies under the EU DTO initiatives and projects

The European Commission has been investing, through the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters work programme, about €15 million annually since 2021 to develop the European Digital Twin Ocean. This complements the €19 million Iliad project, funded under the Green Deal Call for research proposals to pilot the DTO concept, as well as a number of research projects developing the background science¹. Blue-Cloud has proactively started collaboration with a number of those projects, and details are provided below.

5.1. EDITO-Infra

[EDITO-Infra](#) builds the EU Public Infrastructure backbone for the European DTO by upgrading, combining and integrating key service components the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) and the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) into a single digital framework that can be scaled up to an overarching knowledge system, interoperable with Destination Earth.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters/european-digital-twin-ocean-european-dto_en

Blue-Cloud supports the development of applications that could be later deployed on EDITO for sustainability. This was the case of the Zoo and Phytoplankton EOVS demonstrator developed by VLIZ, showcased during the Digital Ocean Forum 2024 in Brussels, which is currently running on both Blue-Cloud and EDITO platforms. The Blue-Cloud and EDITO teams are working on ensuring the most efficient interoperability mechanisms are in place for sharing data, applications and methodologies on both the EDITO and the Blue-Cloud VRE, following the available documentation on the EDITO platform. This will be further detailed within D2.7 due in February 2025.

Besides the simple deployment of Blue-Cloud application/VLabs on EDITO, within the remit of Blue-Cloud 2026 T2.4 “*DTO Taskforce for tuning Blue-Cloud data lakes with DTO developments*”, the teams are investigating technical federation of the Blue-Cloud VRE (powered by D4Science technology) infrastructure with the EDITO platform. The objective is to allow scientists and users to use both infrastructures, selecting the one that best fits their applications or constraints.

EDITO can also expose Blue-Cloud’s method catalogue in EDITO’s process catalogue. Blue-Cloud’s method could be exposed through EDITO’s API and can be launched programmatically from anywhere and run on Blue-Cloud.

Last, for a seamless interoperability with Blue-Cloud, EDITO can use the EOSC’s SSO system, so that a user can easily use both platforms with one single account. This is also currently being discussed in the framework of this collaboration.

5.2. AquaINFRA

AquaINFRA is a project that aims to create a virtual environment to support marine and freshwater scientists in restoring healthy waters. It enables stakeholders to store, share, access, and analyse research data across disciplines and borders, leveraging the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other data spaces. The project focuses on improving collaboration between marine and freshwater communities.

A key goal is to develop an EOSC-based research infrastructure that links marine and freshwater research, providing services for spatio-temporal analysis and modelling through Virtual Research Environments. AquaINFRA will also introduce a cross-country search mechanism and co-design services through use cases, including a Pan-European case and region-specific ones in the Baltic Sea, North Sea, and Mediterranean.

Funded under the same call as Blue-Cloud 2026, AquaINFRA works closely with Blue-Cloud, particularly in the development of services such as Data Discovery and Access Services (DD&AS) and Virtual Research Environments (VRE). The two projects share a common goal of improving marine data interoperability and

quality, with Blue-Cloud's approach being adopted to support AquaINFRA's focus on coastal and inland waters. Additionally, the projects are collaborating to advance the concept of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), fostering technical discussions on how both projects can benefit from shared data and infrastructure.

5.3. DTO-BioFlow

[DTO-BioFlow](#) is dedicated to facilitating access to previously unused marine biodiversity data. It also aims to support the sustainable integration of both existing and new data from various sources. The project encompasses the development of the biological aspects of the DTO, encompassing data flows, models and algorithms.

Blue-Cloud and DTO-BioFlow share some common partners, among which Sorbonne University, which is improving the dataflow from EcoTaxa to EurOBIS (and EMODnet), as well as working in Blue-Cloud Workbench 3, creating biogeographic plankton distribution map data products. There are potential collaborations also between VLIZ LifeWatch data product for DTO-BioFlow and Blue-Cloud VLab 3 on carbon-plankton dynamics, also run by common partners VLIZ and OGS. Another possible liaison is between University of Gottingen and ETHZ and Sorbonne University working on Blue-Cloud Workbench on Ecosystem-level EOVs, that will provide a generic extrapolation tool for maps, which could be useful in DTO-BioFlow to extrapolate habitat distribution maps / abundances as part of University of Gottingen data product.

A first meeting to shape the opportunities for such a collaboration will be organized in early 2025.

6. Collaboration kick-started at the Blue-Cloud first federation workshop

Held at the Instituto Hidrográfico in Lisbon on the 6th of November 2024, the first Blue-Cloud Federation Workshop gathered 40 partners from the Blue-Cloud consortium, together with representatives of marine research infrastructures and initiatives, with the aim to address the need for sharing open science practices and advancements in digital tools and services for European researchers addressing marine and ocean challenges. The Blue-Cloud Federation workshop was the first attempt by Blue-Cloud 2026 to bring together multiple research infrastructures and projects active in the marine and ocean landscape to debate on solutions to innovate and strengthen the FAIRness of their services. The workshop aimed at

assessing Blue-Cloud federated services towards the needs and challenges of other research infrastructures active in marine and climate research, ultimately stimulating a debate around the impact of open science federation in practice.

We like to report about the participation of research infrastructures and projects to the first Federation workshop within this deliverable, since their participation will hopefully represent a start of a more structured collaboration in the near future. The workshop welcomed invited presentations from Research Infrastructures (RIs), projects and initiatives working on marine, environmental and climate related topics. The services and methodologies that they wanted to showcase with the Blue-Cloud community are further detailed in the chapters below.

6.1. CLIMAREST Marine Restoration Toolbox

Lara Veylit, from the CLIMAREST Project, introduced the Marine Restoration Toolbox. This platform serves as a resource for practitioners involved in ecological restoration, and was recently hosted within the Blue-Cloud VRE where it exploits Blue-Cloud computing resources for undertaking some pilot experiments before entering into production.

The marine restoration toolbox was presented as a key innovation from the CLIMAREST project. The toolbox is composed of a website (to be hosted by the Society for Ecological Restoration, SER) which contains resources and networks for marine restoration practitioners and the marine restoration virtual lab hosted by Blue-Cloud 2026 (see MoU described in chapter 4.5 above). In the virtual lab, users can experiment with code and models created in demonstration cases. The demo tool that is available in Blue-Cloud allows users to use Sentinel-2 data (through Copernicus web services) for seagrass area extent monitoring. This represents a low-cost monitoring tool that can be used for intertidal areas and allows for filtering out images where cloud cover or tides obfuscate seagrass cover. A presentation of the website and the co-design process CLIMAREST utilized for creating the website was also provided during the event.

6.2. ICOS RI: ICOS data pipeline

Claudio D’Onofrio, from ICOS ERIC, presented the data lifecycle and quality management processes within ICOS, a network focused on greenhouse gas observation. ICOS has developed a standardised data workflow that ensures data interoperability and traceability, helping to establish the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles as standard practice. ICOS data pipeline allows to provide an open accessible (CC-BY 4.0) near-real-time (NRT) data product, next to the regular annual full quality-controlled Level 2 product. Assuming regular upload is possible from the measurement station (shipboard,

autonomous or buoy), it will be fully automatically processed. The first step includes a verification of transmission and sent to long-term backup facility, then assessed with Quince, an in-house development for quality assurance and quality control. Each step from data transmission to QA/QC data product, is accompanied by references to instruments, calibration protocols, processing methods, platforms, people, etc. A persistent identification (PID) is provided for each stage of the data object for traceability and reproducibility. Finally, a (FAIR) data product is available within 24 hours for download and analysis to the scientific community world-wide.

6.3. LifeWatch federated services: the LifeWatch search engine, the LifeBlock system, the LifeWatch workflow engine

Julio Paneque, from LifeWatch ERIC, presented its federated services, including the LifeWatch search engine, LifeBlock system, and workflow engine. These tools facilitate access to a vast array of biological and environmental data, supporting complex research workflows and promoting data interoperability.

LifeWatch ERIC provides services that allow researchers to gather, manage, store, and analyze FAIR data in a simple way. During the workshop, Julio Paneque presented 3 main services: First, the LifeWatch search engine, which allows to find federated (GBIF, Zenodo, LTER, DiSSCo, and more) and LWE-stored data in a simple, harmonized way. Second, the LifeBlock system, which uses Blockchain to provide traceability and high availability of FAIR data in a distributed way. And third, the LifeWatch workflow engine, which allows researchers to execute data analysis workloads using FAIR data. By combining these three services, researchers are able to find, store, and analyze data to answer relevant environmental questions with it, and publish the results in a trustable, FAIR platform with built-in certification. Based on these FAIR and certified results, policy makers can make sensible decisions for regional or country-level problems, and measure the value of different initiatives based on FAIR indicators.

All the services provided by LifeWatch ERIC are developed with federation in mind. By federating LifeWatch services, other entities can access heterogenous data in a standardized format, execute pre-built workflows that have been scientifically validated, and certify data and workflow results using a FAIR blockchain system. Similarly, LifeWatch ERIC is always looking to federate services from other entities, such as new databases to search within, and specific computational resources that may be needed for special workloads.

6.4. Euro-Argo platform and a global network contributing to the Global Ocean Observing System and the Global Climate Observing System

Euro-ARGO ERIC, represented by Yann-Hervé De Roeck, presented its platform and global network contributing to the Global Ocean Observing System and the Global Climate Observing System. The Euro-Argo ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) allows active coordination and strengthening of the European contribution to the international Argo programme. Contributing to the Global Ocean Observing System and the Global Climate Observing System, Argo is characterised by the combination of a specific autonomous platform and a global network.

The platform (Argo float) performs vertical profiles of the water column, collecting every 10 days the following set of essential environmental variables from the surface to -2000m to -6000m: temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a, pH, nitrates, particles, irradiance (light). The network consists of 4000 floats drifting in the global ocean, providing more than 100000 profiles per year, more than 3 million since its inception. The geographical boundary is now the permanently ice-covered regions and the coastal shelves. On the fourth of this fleet, Euro-Argo ERIC deploys, manages and enhances the technical and procedural components of the system.

All data have always been open and free. Operational users (for weather and ocean forecasting, Copernicus CMEMS) have access, with a maximum delay of 6 hours, to automatically quality-controlled data provided by 400 emerging platforms per day, via the WMO GTS, as well as from the Global Data Assembly Centres (2 replicates in Europe and the USA). Scientific users (as well as the public at large) have at their disposal expertly quality controlled data (updated once a year) through several portals which, in fine point to the GDACs (EMODnet, SeaDataNet) and EOSC related projects (ENVRI-Hub Next, ENVRI-FAIR, Blue Cloud), help to develop the data discovery map, service access and VRE.

6.5. EMSO ERIC Data Federation and Management via ERDDAP

Ingrid Puillat, EMSO ERIC Director General, presented the evolution of EMSO's IT infrastructure, which currently leverages a federated ERDDAP system to enhance data distribution and retrieval of its operative sites across Europe, while optimising data access and ensuring data sustainability.

7. Collaboration with other projects and initiatives

In addition to the initiatives mentioned above, Blue-Cloud has begun exploring collaboration opportunities with other EU-funded projects. The following paragraphs outline the current status of these collaborations.

7.1. AQUARIUS

[AQUARIUS](#) is a Horizon Europe project that supports large-scale, multidisciplinary projects through Transnational Access (TA) calls, which encourage collaboration among scientific teams and focus on filling data gaps in key marine regions. The data collected will be integrated into major European infrastructures such as SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, and Copernicus INSTAC, ensuring high-quality, accessible, and long-term data stewardship. To assist researchers, AQUARIUS provides dedicated data management support, with experts from leading European data infrastructures offering training and guidance on data standards, services, and best practices. This network helps ensure the efficient use of collected data and promotes its integration into global platforms like EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, and the European Digital Twin Ocean.

In the latter stages of the project, AQUARIUS will establish major synergies with Blue-Cloud 2026 to promote open science practices. This collaboration includes:

- Training TA scientific teams in the use of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and its Virtual Laboratories (VLabs);
- Encouraging TA scientific teams to explore the Blue-Cloud VRE's potential by combining their newly collected data with existing datasets and analytical workflows.

This collaboration will bring twofold benefits: it will help increase the number of researchers engaging with the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform and introduce early-career scientists to open science practices, fostering a culture of collaboration and data-sharing across the research community.

7.2. AtlantECO

The EU-funded AtlantECO project aims to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework that provides knowledge-based resources for a better understanding and management of the Atlantic Ocean and its ecosystem services. AtlantECO will engage with citizens and actors from the industry and policy sectors in order to stimulate responsible behaviour and Blue Growth. The project focuses on three pillars of

research: microbiomes, plastic and the plastisphere, and seascape connectivity. In pursuit of this goal, AtlantECO is bringing together experts and pioneers from Europe, South America and South Africa with the relevant resources, knowledge and experience.

[AtlantECO](#) aims to leverage the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS) results to integrate imaging, genomics, and environmental data, while running its data analysis pipelines and delivering the resulting data products for EMODnet. Additionally, AtlantECO is significantly enhancing the data available to Blue-Cloud and its demonstrators ([Plankton Genomics](#), [Carbon-Plankton Dynamics](#)) and WorkBench ([Ecosystem-level EOVs](#)) through its systematic and harmonised data management processes, covering various cruises and sampling campaigns. Its newly collected datasets are uploaded into Blue Data Infrastructures such as EurOBIS and ELIXIR - ENA, making them part of the Blue-Cloud DD&AS offering.

Blue-Cloud benefits from AtlantECO by gaining access to new data on microbiomes, the plastisphere, and carbon fluxes, which support ecosystems at a basin level. Furthermore, AtlantECO's predictions on the cumulative impacts of multiple stressors on ecosystem status, dynamics, and ecosystem service provision provide valuable insights. These predictions help identify key drivers and assess their role in tipping points, as well as their effects on the recovery of ecosystem structures, functions, and services. AtlantECO also develops eco-socioeconomic models to predict future trajectories. These factors significantly influence the Blue ecosystem, and therefore have the potential to impact the results produced by the Blue-Cloud VLabs.

7.3. Blue Remediomics

The [BlueRemediomics](#) project develops innovative tools and methodologies to explore marine microbiome data, bringing together an international consortium of experts to focus on the discovery and production of high-value, sustainable products, processes, and services based on marine microbiomes.

The project's aim is to enhance knowledge and data that support the development of legislative frameworks for better monitoring, understanding, and safeguarding the marine microbiome. Additionally, BlueRemediomics strives to enable the sustainable and equitable exploitation of marine microbiomes, setting the foundation for producing novel, natural, and sustainable products derived from marine bioresources.

BlueRemediomics works with aquaculture data, which will be integrated into Blue-Cloud 2026 via MGnify. This data will connect to the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS) and will populate the Workbench on Ecosystem-level Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

As a sister project to AtlantECO, BlueRemediomics prioritises FAIR data principles and will focus on improving the FAIRness of data within the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs (VLabs). Specifically, it will test and enhance the FAIR data management of VLabs related to Plankton Genomics and Aquaculture Monitoring. In addition, BlueRemediomics is interested in testing the Marine Environmental Indicators and Carbon-Plankton Dynamics VLabs.

7.4. BRIDGE-BS

BRIDGE-BS is an innovative initiative focused on promoting sustainable blue growth in the Black Sea region through three interconnected nodes:

- *NODE 1: Ecosystem Service Dynamics* – This node aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of ecosystem functioning, which will enable adaptive management practices for the region’s marine environment.
- *NODE 2: Blue Growth Incubators* – Aimed at translating scientific innovations into viable business opportunities, this node helps drive economic growth within the ocean economy.
- *NODE 3: Empowered Citizens* – This node focuses on building a knowledgeable and cohesive Black Sea community, engaging scientists, policymakers, entrepreneurs, and the wider public.

By fostering collaboration among stakeholders and encouraging knowledge exchange, BRIDGE-BS seeks to pave the way for a sustainable blue economy in the Black Sea region. Its main goals include:

- Building an informed and empowered Black Sea community,
- Fostering cooperation between scientists, policymakers, and entrepreneurs,
- Ensuring sustainability and preparing for future marine environmental challenges.

BRIDGE-BS has adopted the SeaDataNet Common Data Index (CDI) service to facilitate the discovery and access of new marine data related to the Black Sea region. This ensures that these datasets seamlessly integrate into established data repositories such as EMODnet and the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS), making them readily available for stakeholders.

Additionally, BRIDGE-BS has tailored the CDI service to offer a dedicated Black Sea User Interface, accessible via the BRIDGE-BS website. This interface simplifies access to marine data specific to the Black Sea, improving the usability and accessibility for users in the region.

Looking ahead, BRIDGE-BS is also exploring the development of Virtual Research Environments (VREs) with plans for further integration and expansion. These efforts highlight BRIDGE-BS’s commitment to fostering collaboration, innovation, and sustainability within the Black Sea’s marine ecosystem.

7.5. CODE BLUE

[CODE BLUE](#) is an innovative initiative aimed at tackling the complex challenges facing our world through collaboration and the application of advanced technology. By bringing together diverse perspectives and expertise, CODE BLUE strives to create impactful solutions in areas such as science, knowledge transfer, software development, sustainability, and innovation. A key event driving these efforts is the Blue Biotech Hackathon, organised in October 2024, which will bring together researchers, developers, and innovators to collaborate and generate solutions for the blue economy.

In support of the [Blue Biotech Hackathon](#), Blue-Cloud has provided a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for all participants. This virtual platform allowed researchers and innovators to perform analyses and tests across a range of fields, including biotechnology, marine science, and industry. By leveraging the Blue-Cloud VRE, teams had access to high-quality datasets and advanced analytical tools, empowering them to develop innovative solutions for sustainable marine practices. This collaboration underscored Blue-Cloud's commitment to facilitating cutting-edge research and innovation in the blue economy.

8. Conclusions

The first release of the Blue-Cloud Stakeholder Engagement and Synergies report provides an overview of the synergies established with EU-funded projects and initiatives. Building these synergies has helped the project team expand Blue-Cloud's impact within the research community. By collaborating with similar initiatives in the same research field, the project can share its results with a broader audience, ensuring its outcomes are more widely recognised and not isolated.

In the second half of the project's lifespan, the team will continue to identify and engage with relevant initiatives in open science, marine research, and blue economy, fostering both technical and outreach collaborations. The team will maintain the same approach to cooperation as it has so far. Moving forward, the focus will be on strengthening Blue-Cloud's position in open science and the European Digital Twin of the Ocean by further aligning with EDITO developments and enhancing the interoperability of its data federation mechanisms and services.